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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

Abbreviation	Definition
CSV	Comma Separated Values file
CTA	Clinical trial application
DMP	Data management plan
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
FAIR	Findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability
OA	Open Access
OAI-PMH	Open Archive Initiative - Protocol for Metadata Harvesting

CONTENTS

1.	Data summary	5
2.	Fair data	7
3.	Allocation of resources.....	8
4.	Data Description.....	8
5.	WP1 Pilot scale designs and optimization for IMTAbased systems	8
5.1.	Task 1.1. Present production (Lead: [UGE]).....	8
5.2.	Task 1.2 Site selection, species, and engineering layout (Lead: [UGE])	11
5.3.	Task 1.3 Growth modeling for individual species (Lead: [LLE])	13
6.	WP2 Operation and evaluation of IMTA upscaled designs	15
6.1.	Task 2.1 Modeling of upscaled IMTA designs (Lead: [LLE])	15
6.3.	Task 2.2 Implementation, monitoring, assessment of performance (Lead: [TSCG])	17
6.4.	Task 2.3 Evaluation of the economics of IMTA systems (Lead: [HOL])	19
6.5.	Task 2.4 Environmental modeling and integration in management systems and decision-making (Lead: [LLE])	20
7.	WP3 Finetuning and design of added-value eco-production systems and evaluation of pilot scale operation	21
7.1.	Task 3.1 Macroalgae cultivation for eco-packaging purposes (Lead: [AWI])	22
7.2.	Task 3.2 Upscaling the beach wracks valorization process (Lead: [UROS])	22
7.3.	Task 3.3 Upscaling low-cost microalgae production process (Lead: [UCC]).....	23
7.5.	Task 3.4 Upscaling a macroalgae cultivation methodology in liquid wastes (Lead: [CUT])	24
7.6.	Task 3.5 Upscaling seaweed cultivation in earthen ponds (Lead: [CTQ])	25
8.	WP4 Verification of existing & new developments for processing algae, fish, and extraction of compounds.....	26
8.1.	Task 4.1. Modeling and simulation of biorefinery processes for an optimized upscaling (Lead: [IDE])	26
8.2.	Task 4.2. Drying and microwave enhancement (Lead: [IDE]).....	27
8.3.	Task 4.3. Microwave commission and finetuning (Lead: [IDE]).....	28
8.4.	Task 4.4. Verification of an existing process for protein ingredients production from fish (Leader – [BII])	28
8.5.	Task 4.5 Demonstrating the bacterial-based algal-polysaccharides decomposition for improving algae nutritional value and digestibility (Lead: [IOLR])	29
8.6.	Task 4.6 Finetuning and upscaling of the bacterial-enzymatic reactor for algae decomposition (Lead: [IOLR])	30
8.7.	Task 4.7 Macroalgae-based eco-packaging boxes (Lead: [AWI]).....	30

8.8.	Task 4.8 Upscaling a methodology for bycatch and algae biomass processing and valorization (Lead: [CTQ])	30
9.	WP5 Properties evaluation, formulation, novel functional products, and biosecurity	31
9.1.	Task 5.1 Evaluation of algae and extracts properties (Lead: [UGE])	31
9.2.	Task 5.2 Formulation, development, and validation of innovative aquafeeds (Lead: CTQ) 32	
9.4.	Task 5.3 Formulation, development, and validation of functional food for human consumption (Lead: TUCN)	34
9.5.	Task 5.4 Biosecurity assessments for new products (Lead: [ANF])	36
10.	WP6 IT tools development and monitoring for traceability and enhanced trust	37
10.1.	Task 6.1. Optimized models for circularity in aquaculture (Lead: [ITE]).....	37
10.2.	Task 6.2. Monitoring systems for complete traceability (Lead: [ITE])	38
10.3.	Task 6.3. NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace digital platform (Lead: [IT]).....	38
10.4.	Task 6.4. NOVAFOODIES App for end-users (Lead: [IT]).....	39
12.	WP7 Value chain sustainability, socio-laboral inclusion and standardization	40
12.1.	Task 7.1 Environmental impacts evaluation (LCA) (Lead: [HOL]).....	40
12.2.	Task 7.2 Economic impacts evaluation (LCC) (Lead: [HOL])	40
12.3.	Task 7.3 Social and Gender Assessments (Lead: [ACH]).....	41
12.4.	Task 7.4 Training activities (Lead: [LVA])	42
12.5.	Task 7.5 Standardisation roadmap (Lead: [ASRO]).....	44
13.	WP8 Dissemination, exploitation, clustering, and engagement	44
13.2.	Task 8.1 Plan for exploitation and dissemination of results (PEDR) (Lead: [LCI])	45
13.3.	Task 8.2 Communication and dissemination activities (Lead: [SPES]).....	45
13.4.	Task 8.3 Clustering activities (Lead: [SPES]).....	46
13.5.	Task 8.4 IP management, Exploitation of results and business models (Lead: [LCI]) ...	46
13.6.	Task 8.5 Stakeholder engagement and co-creation (Lead: [SPES]).....	47
14.	WP9 Project management	47
14.1.	Task 9.1 Overall coordination (Lead: [IDE])	47
14.2.	Task 9.2 Financial and administrative management (Lead: [IDE]).....	47
14.3.	Task 9.3 Data Management (Lead: [LCI])	48
15.	Data storage timeline.....	48

1. Data summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) for the NOVEFOODIES project is developed to facilitate data flow and utilization of the data between the parties, including third parties/public where appropriate, and ensure proper data preservation for future use. DMP is developed in line with the Guidelines on FAIR Data Management in Horizon Europe projects. The purpose of the DMP is to cover the complete research data life cycle and to describe the types of data that will be generated/collected during the project, the standards that will be used, how data will be preserved, and what parts will be shared for verification or use. the Data Management Plan-DMP, which will ensure all data is collected, stored, and used in compliance with GDPR. Besides, the DMP will detail how the project members will carry out the planned data collection and data processing operations. In this sense, all beneficiaries confirm GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) compliance, including relevant systems and privacy practices, and deploy privacy by design and privacy by default. With all these tools, the involved partners in collecting the data will supervise and monitor that the rights, freedom, and ownership of the data of all the individuals who participate directly or indirectly in the project are ensured.

The details of the Data Management Plan are demonstrated in the Grant Agreement, Task 9.3: Data generated through the project lifetime will be analyzed and a comprehensive DMP will be delivered at M6, identifying best practices and specific standards to be applied to the R&D data collected in relevant WPs, considering the actual EU guidelines about the format, storage & curation. These practices will ensure the data's suitability for sharing and reuse by existing legislation and guidelines from public authorities. A data repository will be available at M8, conforming to applicable laws and ethical guidelines. DMP will detail the format of the quantitative scientific data, results of statistical analyses, and anonymized data that will be included in the repository.

Open Science Practices

NOVAFOODIES consortium will integrate an open science approach to the scientific process based on transparent cooperative work, tools, and knowledge diffusion. Achieving the project objectives relies on solid collaboration, including the sharing of data, knowledge, and materials. The open science approach will start within the consortium to increase the quality, efficiency, and accuracy of results. The partners commit to using common data standards, open software as much as possible, and open protocols. The open approach outside the consortium will make our results more reliable, impactful, and better understandable by society. The key elements of the open science approach are:

Open access to scientific publications: The consortium will ensure immediate open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications generated in the project (at the latest at the time of publication) via Zenodo, an OpenAIRE-compliant repository, and institutional repositories, such as the *Cork Open Research Archive* from [UCC], *Pangaea* from [AWI] or *Med Iter Haifa* from [UH]. Publications deposited in Zenodo will be automatically indexed in OpenAIRE to ensure the largest possible impact. Each partner will provide information about any research output, tool, or instrument needed to validate the conclusions of the publication via the repository. The deposited publications will be identified through accessible bibliographic metadata, including the terms European Union and Horizon Europe; the name of the action, acronym, and grant number; publication date; and a persistent identifier, e.g., DOI. The publication in Open Research Europe will be favored.

Open access to research data: The consortium will provide open access to research data and other outputs (e.g., software, models, algorithms, workflows) following the principle “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. All data or other results needed for validation of conclusions of peer-reviewed publications will be granted open access through Zenodo. The consortium partners will ensure that the publications refer to the availability of such data (e.g., referring to the DOI identifier of the data). Readers will be able to access the data underpinning the results presented in any publications, ensuring reproducibility and transferability (or interoperability) for all potential users, academic, industry, and citizen scientists. The access conditions to other data generated in the project will be detailed in the Data Management Plan (**Deliverable 9.1**). Open access to research data will be preferred and exceptions will only be allowed for valid reasons relating to data protection rules, security interests, IPR, EU global economic competitiveness, and other legitimate interests. European Open Science Cloud will also be used when possible.

Responsible research data management: The consortium will manage the data responsibly and in line with FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Principles. Following these principles will facilitate the collaboration and data sharing between partners to deliver the project outputs with the highest quality as well as the traceability, reproducibility, and reusability of data beyond the project. The data management strategy will be outlined in the DMP (see **Section 1.2.7** which is following for more details).

Other open science practices: The consortium will promote engagement in other open science practices, such as participation in citizen science actions, open peer-review, sharing of pre-prints (e.g., in arXiv, bioRxiv) and protocols, workflows, and analytic scripts (e.g., in GitHub). These practices will not only increase the visibility and re-usability of the research outputs, but also the reproducibility and replicability, and the excellence and impact of the results. The participants have a strong track record in these practices. The open science practices will be part of a broader **Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI)** approach that will promote stakeholder engagement, through communication and dissemination actions; gender equality, through the promotion of gender balance in R&D teams and decision-making processes; science education, through participatory research agendas and training activities for the engagement of students and young researchers; and ethics and research integrity, through continuous orientation, reflection and deliberation on the decisions, actions and values of the consortium.

Management of research data and other research outputs

NOVAFOODIES is a data-intensive initiative, relying on the generation, sharing, and analysis of large amounts of data. Thus, data management is a key aspect of the methodology, which will follow the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Data Principles. **Task 9.3** will develop a **DMP**, delivering the 1st version by M6 (**D9.1**) and updating it throughout the project. DMP will describe the steps to ensure FAIR principles over the data life cycle. The consortium has identified the main types of data that will be produced and re-used (**Table 1.1**). The form of the data will usually determine the format (i.e., file extension).

Table 1. The main types of data that will be handled within the NOVAFOODIES project

Observational	Captured in real-time, typically outside the laboratory, e.g., sensor readings, plants operation, survey results, images, etc., will be e.g., generated in WP1, WP2, WP3, and WP4 as a result of the demo activities in a relevant environment, and in WP8 where surveys to stakeholders will take place.
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Experimental	Collected under controlled conditions, e.g., finetuning experiments in WP1, WP2, and WP4 ; products characterization and biosecurity assessments during WP5 .
Simulation	They are generated by the models produced within the project. These data will be reproducible if the model and inputs are preserved. Simulation data will be mainly generated in WP1, WP2, WP4, WP6, WP7 .
Derived	Generated by existing datasets and reproducible. Derived data from experimental datasets may be used, e.g., as inputs for modeling in WP1, WP2, and WP6 ; LCA and LCC in WP6 .
Reference or canonical	Static or organic collection (peer-reviewed) datasets are most probably published and/or curated. This type of data will be used together with experimental data as input for the modeling activities.

2. Fair data

To facilitate the management according to FAIR principles, **the consortium will use the Communities functionality of Zenodo (free-of-charge, funded by the EC and managed by CERN) to deposit publications, data, and other outputs for sharing** in a common project repository. [LCI] will manage the **NOVAFOODIES** data repository (launched by M8) and oversee that the uploaded data complies with the principles defined in the DMP, while each partner will appoint one data management responsible within their organization.

F

Findability: Each item deposited in Zenodo will be issued a persistent and unique identifier (i.e., a DOI). All project records will be described with metadata that will ease the findability (e.g., data description, keywords, project acronym) and will be linked to the ORCID of the researchers who produced the data to ensure traceability. Data deposited in Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository (20 years at least).

A

Accessibility: At the time of deposit, each item will be granted either open, closed, or embargoed access as per the provisions in the DMP and the IP management strategy. The reasons for closed data will be clearly explained in the DMP and will comply with the legitimate reasons allowed by the EC. Any data needed to validate the results published in peer-reviewed publications will be granted open access through Zenodo.

I

Interoperability: The preferred data formats will be those facilitating the data interoperability, i.e., nonproprietary; open, documented standards; in common usage by the research community; using standard character encodings (ASCII, UTF-8); and preferably uncompressed. The data deposited in Zenodo will be described with rich metadata compliant with DataCite's Metadata Schema. Also, **NOVAFOODIES** will comply with European and international standards to set a common research data terminology within the specific fields, e.g.: bio-based products (CEN/TC 411), environmental management (CEN/SS S26), waste management (CEN/TC 183), units and symbols (CEN/SS F02), energy efficiency and saving calculation (CEN/CLC/JWG 4).

R

Reusability: Open data deposited in Zenodo will be released with a CC BY license or equivalent. If specific software or tools are needed to access or re-use the data, information about these will be

provided in a complementary text file. Deposited closed data will indicate the reusability conditions (license) under which these data can be accessed and how these data can be requested.

3. Allocation of resources

All partners are requested to collect and manage the data by the DMP and other common professional practices, especially the task leaders. The WP leaders will be responsible for the implementation of the DMP and will monitor data management activities.

4. Data Description

The list of WPs is presented in Table 2 and Data management is included in all of them.

Table 2. List of WPs

WP	Lead beneficiary
WP1	UGE
WP2	TSCG
WP3	AWI
WP4	IDE
WP5	CTQ
WP6	ITE
WP7	HOL
WP8	LCI
WP9	IDE

5. WP1 Pilot scale designs and optimization for IMTAbased systems

WP1 aims to design the IMTA layout for the involved farms in Europe, Israel, and China, addressing species, site selection, and technological features to optimize add-on species production. The sites where IMTA is implemented are different in terms of environmental features, production system and intensity/effort, husbandry practice, and farm size.

5.1. Task 1.1. Present production (Lead: [UGE])

Partners involved: UGE, UH, YSFRI, KEF, UT, SGM

UGE Optimization and pilot scale design for IMTA systems
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the pilot scale designs and optimization for IMTA-based systems will be created, analyzed, and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?

Raw data from analytical evaluations, processed data in Office Excel, Word, and PowerPoint documents, and data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 15 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties upon request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in case they will be published on Open Access journals, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners.

UH Implementation, monitoring, and performance evaluation
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Record of the setup of the IMTA system
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word and PPT
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 2 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
In peer review Journal

YSFRI Task 1.1 Present production Task 1.2 Site selection, species, and engineering layout
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the designs and optimization for IMTA-based systems will be created and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?

<p>Emails and Word/excel documents during the communication process will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator. Some environmental/culture organism growth data collected during the project (excel file, NetCDF file, txt file) will be stored on the NAS server at YSFRI.</p>
<p>Where will it be stored?</p>
<p>On the server located in YSFRI in Qingdao.</p>
<p>Will you re-use any existing data and how?</p>
<p>Some previous observation data will be used to compare with newly collected data.</p>
<p>What is the expected size of the data?</p>
<p>The reserved space for this data is 10 GB.</p>
<p>To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?</p>
<p>To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?</p>
<p>Data can be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. However the access needs to be granted by the YSFRI data management authorities, and we need to be authorized to share the data with our European partners.</p>
<p>Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?</p>
<p>No.</p>

<p>KEF Task 1.1 Task 1.2</p>
<p>What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>
<p>Data related to the designs and optimization for IMTA-based systems will be created and stored.</p>
<p>What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?</p>
<p>Emails and Word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.</p>
<p>Where will it be stored?</p>
<p>On our server.</p>
<p>Will you re-use any existing data and how?</p>
<p>All data will be novel.</p>
<p>What is the expected size of the data?</p>
<p>The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.</p>
<p>Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?</p>
<p>To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?</p>
<p>Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.</p>
<p>Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?</p>
<p>No.</p>

<p>UT</p>
<p>What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?</p>
<p>Data will be collected from the performance of the experimental IMTA system for further analyses</p>

What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents, reports, and digital data on farm performance.
Where will it be stored?
Internal server of Estonian Marine Institute, University of Tartu
What is the expected size of the data?
6 MB
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Will synthesize data from previous projects and database
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes. Will publish reports

SGM
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to current production, farm details and farming practice
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Excel template files, filled and stored on a shared folder in Dropbox, and the cloud storage of Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Some data is available from previous work, some will be updated.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

5.2. Task 1.2 Site selection, species and engineering layout (Lead: [UGE])

Partners involved: UGE, UH, KEF – Data Management was already provided combined with Task 1.1., YSFRI - Data Management was already provided combined with Task 1.1., UT, SGM

UGE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the site selection, species and engineering layout will be created, analyzed, and stored.

What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Raw data from analytical evaluations, processed data in Office Excel, Word, and PowerPoint documents, and data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 15 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties upon request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in case they will be published on Open Access journals, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners.

UH
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Engineering design of the IMTA
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word and PPT doc
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 1GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
In peer review Journal

UT
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected from performance of the experimental IMTA system for further analyses
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents, reports
Where will it be stored?
Internal server of Estonian Marine Institute, University of Tartu

What is the expected size of the data?
6 MB
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Will synthesize data from previous projects and databases.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes. Will publish reports

SGM
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected to evaluate the best potential sites at the farm scale, to deploy the IMTA species. Explore the best layout according to species and engineering improvements.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Data loggers files, excel files, .csv files. They are stored in a shared folder in Dropbox, and the cloud storage of Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Some environmental data is available from previous works, but most will be novel.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, only a partial part of the data (e.g environmental)

5.3. Task 1.3 Growth modeling for individual species (Lead: [LLE])

Partners involved: INALE, LLE, SGM

LLE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
In this task, LLE will be collecting data from the different WP1 partners and from the literature to develop individual growth models for species of seaweeds, fish, shellfish, and detritivores.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents and Excel files with model inputs and outputs will be generated and stored on the cloud (Dropbox and Box).
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Some of the individual growth models to be developed in this task will build on physiological data and knowledge from previous projects. All the model setups and modeling results will be novel. The code and modeling tools to be used in this task are proprietary to Longline Environment. The modeling tools will be shared with project partners under request.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
Model setups and outputs will be shared exclusively with project partners in the conditions specified in the project
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Some metadata may be public, subject to partner (e.g. farm owner) approval.

INALE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data collection and generation in this project serve the purpose of supporting growth modeling for individual species. These data are integral to achieving our project objective.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Data on modeling of seasonal seaweed growth by estimating their potential monthly yields to support model-based optimization of production systems and upscaling designs will be produced in Excel files and Word documents and will be stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?
On the INALE server and clouds hosted by the coordinator.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
We will use data from previous projects to model Mediterranean seaweed species about temperature.
What is the expected size of the data?
Limited space is required; 1 GB should be sufficient.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Our data are subject to patents and joint publications, so no other parties can have access to them.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in some cases, to engage the citizens, but data in terms of communication rather than dissemination.

SGM
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected to support the growth models developed by the LLE partner.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?

Excel files with metadata to feed into the FARM model. They are stored in a shared folder in Dropbox, and the cloud storage of Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Mussel growth data to support the modeling is available from previous work. For other species, data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Not directly. Maybe other partners might publish e.g LLE modeling

6. WP2 Operation and evaluation of IMTA upscaled designs

WP2 carries out the operation of designed IMTA systems in WP1 to validate them and reach the target scale of production, monitor, and evaluate the environmental and economic gains for a profitable IMTA development in each of the case studies, performing relevant changes in the designs if needed, supporting the adoption of IMTA systems in Europe and paving the way for the market uptake, and providing appropriate biomass of cultured species to other WPs to perform their activities.

6.1. Task 2.1 Modeling of upscaled IMTA designs (Lead: [LLE])

Partner involved: LLE, UT, SGM

LLE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The individual growth models developed under WP1 will be used to run the ORGANIX deposition model. Data on bathymetry and residual currents will be collected from project partners and used as input to the ORGANIX model. The modeling outputs from Task 2.1 and the results from ORGANIX will be used to optimize the design of 3 selected IMTA systems.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents and Excel files with model inputs and outputs will be generated and stored on the cloud (Dropbox and Box).
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Longline may use data and knowledge from previous projects to develop this task, but the resulting models will be novel. All modeling setups and results will be novel. The code and modeling tools to be used in this task are proprietary to Longline Environment.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.

Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
Model setups and outputs will be shared exclusively with project partners in the conditions specified in the project
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Some metadata may be public, subject to partner (e.g. farm owner) approval.

UT
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected from performance of the experimental IMTA system for further analyses and modeling
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents, reports, database
Where will it be stored?
Internal server of Estonian Marine Institute, University of Tartu
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Will synthesize data from previous projects and database
What is the expected size of the data?
6 MB
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes. Will publish reports

SGM
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected to support the growth models developed by LLE partners.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Excel files with metadata to feed into the FARM model. They are stored in a shared folder in Dropbox, and the cloud storage of Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The data generated here will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?

Not directly.

6.2. Task 2.2 Implementation, monitoring, and assessment of performance (Lead: [TSCG])

Partners involved: TSCG, UH, KEF, YSFRI, UT, SGM

TSCG
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data is collected to form a baseline of environmental (abiotic and biotic) parameters and throughout the project measure environmental changes /impact on trophic systems (fish, shellfish, and seaweed) in respect of nutrient fluxes, carrying capacity uptake, etc. Do model performance and improvements on biomass generation and economics
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails and Word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator. Environmental data (e.g. temp loggers) will downloaded into Excel and stored in the first instance on the company's SharePoint drive and relevant information stored in the host organisation's SharePoint file system
Where will it be stored?
On our server and the host coordinator sharepoint file system.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
For the baseline, we will use as much possible existing data that is available, while in parallel we started with monthly measuring of environmental parameters (biotic and abiotic) which will be new data.
What is the expected size of the data?
Not more than a few GB incl the raw data from loggers and nutrient analysis
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only especially to Holos and Long line Environment as they need this for their modeling. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request (State Agencies e.g.). Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, as we want the IMTA concept to be adopted by the aquaculture society as common practice. Think in terms of policy papers, conferences, etc.

YSFRI
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to operation and evaluation of IMTA upscaled designs will be created and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
The environmental/culture organism growth data collected during the project (excel file, NetCDF file, txt file) will be stored on the NAS server at YSFRI.
Where will it be stored?
On the server located in YSFRI in Qingdao.

Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Some previous observation data will be used to compare with newly collected environmental and organism growth data.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 10 GB.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data can be accessible to the project partners only on request. However, the access needs to be granted by the YSFRI data management authorities, we need to apply to our information center to share the data with our European partners.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

UH
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Optimizing IMTA systems
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word and PPT
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 2 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
In peer review Journal

UT
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Environmental monitoring and farm performance data will be collected from the experimental IMTA system for further analyses and modeling
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents, reports, database
Where will it be stored?
Internal server of Estonian Marine Institute, University of Tartu
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Will synthesize data from previous projects and database
What is the expected size of the data?
6 MB

To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes. Will publish reports

SGM
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected to monitor and assess the performance of implementation
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Excel files. Csv files are Stored in a shared folder in Dropbox, and the cloud storage of Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The data generated here will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

6.3. Task 2.3 Evaluation of the economics of IMTA systems (Lead: [HOL])

Partner involved: HOL, SGM

HOL
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The data collected from the partners and the process will be used to elaborate on the economic potential of the IMTA upscaled systems.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, Excel, and Word documents, as well as reports, should be produced and saved inside the cloud storage systems provided by Microsoft, such as Outlook, Teams/SharePoint, or ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All of the data collected for this study will be entirely novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The allotted storage capacity for this material is 6GB if necessary.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?

Data will be accessible to the project partners.
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
According to the Grant Agreement, Data and Deliverables were classified as Sensitive.

SGM
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected to support economic assessment of systems
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word, and Excel files. Csv files are Stored in a shared folder in Dropbox, and the cloud storage of Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The data generated here will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No

6.4. Task 2.4 Environmental modeling and integration in management systems and decision-making (Lead: [LLE])

Partner involved: LLE, SGM

LLE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The individual growth models developed under WP1 will be used to run the ORGANIX deposition model. Data on bathymetry and residual currents will be collected from project partners and used as an input to the ORGANIX model. The modeling outputs from Task 2.1 and the results from ORGANIX will be used to optimize the design of 3 selected IMTA systems.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents and Excel files with model inputs and outputs will be generated and stored on the cloud (Dropbox and Box).
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Longline may use data and knowledge from previous projects to develop this task, but the resulted models will be novel. All modeling setups and results will be novel. The code and modeling tools to be used in this task are proprietary to Longline Environment.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
Model setups and outputs will be shared exclusively within project partners in the conditions specified in the project
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Some metadata may be public, subject to partner (e.g. farm owner) approval.

SGM
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data will be collected to support the ORGANIX deposition model
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Excel files. Csv files, Metadata for the model. Stored in a shared folder in Dropbox, and the cloud storage of Microsoft SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The data generated here will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Access will be granted by the project manager.
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes. Potentially some environmental data could be published.

7. WP3 Finetuning and design of added-value eco-production systems and evaluation of pilot scale operation

WP3 aims to optimise production systems at TRL6-7 paving the way for an industrial scale. This WP will send samples from each task with WP4 and WP5 partners for further activities following the Nagoya protocol.

7.1. Task 3.1 Macroalgae cultivation for eco-packaging purposes (Lead: [AWI])

Partner involved: AWI

AWI
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the macroalgae cultivation for eco-packaging purposes will be created, stored, presented at international conferences, used for educational purposes, and published in open-access journals (as appropriate).
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, word documents, excel spreadsheets, PowerPoint presentations will be generated and stored on the cloud storage of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On SharePoint and the AWI server
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 10 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only until open-access publication. Before publication, non-sensitive data will be accessible to interested official parties on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes

7.2. Task 3.2 Upscaling the beach wracks valorization process (Lead: [UROS])

Partner involved: UROS

UROS
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Project-related data will be used to reach the work package and project goals. Therefore, they will be collected, stored, and archived. Additional use will be made to present the project/work package and its outcome at international conferences and meetings. At the local University, data might be used for educational purposes and, if applicable, for publication in open-source and peer-reviewed journals.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Experimental setup files, protocols, and notes will be stored in MS Office format and stored on the local hard drive, the University's remote server, and/or project sharing platform, hosted by the project coordinator. The same counts for emails.
Where will it be stored?
On the local hard drive and/or the University's remote server
Will you re-use any existing data and how?

Previous gained data on seasonal beach wrack patterns might be used, additional data will be novel and gained through the project.
What is the expected size of the data?
The capacity for project data is appx. 10 GB on the University's server and up to 2 TB on external hard drives (i.e. for pictures etc.).
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only before publication. Data, especially non-sensitive data, might be issued to interested official parties on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, most likely

7.3.Task 3.3 Upscaling low-cost microalgae production process (Lead: [UCC])

Partner involved: UCC

UCC
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The optimization of low-cost microalgae production process for individual microalgae species under natural sunlight
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Numeric Excel databases, powerpoints, and Word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 8 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes

7.5. Task 3.4 Upscaling a macroalgae cultivation methodology in liquid wastes (Lead: [CUT])

Partners involved: CUT, INALE

CUT
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data collection and generation in this project serve the purpose of supporting the upscaling of the macroalgae cultivation methodology in liquid wastes. These data are integral to achieving our project objective.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
The project will generate data related to: a) The optimization of <i>Cladophora</i> sp. cultivation at the laboratory scale, including activities such as strain isolation, unialgal cultivation, and phenotyping concerning abiotic factors. b) The optimization and upscaling of <i>Cladophora</i> sp. cultivation in high-quality liquid waste streams within an open-air algal technology system. This includes biomass characterization in WP5 and an assessment of its properties. These data will be recorded in Excel files and Word documents, and they will be stored in cloud storage systems such as Microsoft (e.g., Outlook, Teams/SharePoint) and ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?
The data will be stored on servers hosted by CUT and INALE, as well as on cloud storage platforms managed by the project coordinator.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
We will utilize data from previous projects to optimize the growth conditions in both laboratory and open-air systems, particularly in the context of high-quality liquid waste streams. Additionally, data generated from our pilot experiments will also be integrated into our analysis and decision-making processes.
What is the expected size of the data?
Given that we will be handling videos and photos, each partner (CUT, INALE) should allocate approximately 10 GB of storage space.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
The data will be accessible exclusively to project partners. Our data are subject to patents and joint publications; thus access is restricted to the project consortium, and no other external parties will have access.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in some cases we will generate data intended for public engagement. However, this data will primarily serve communication purposes rather than wide-scale dissemination.

INALE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data in upscaling the macroalgae cultivation methodology in liquid wastes is collected and generated. These data are integral to achieving our project objective.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?

Data on modeling of seasonal seaweed growth by estimating their potential monthly yields to support model-based optimization of production systems and upscaling designs will be produced in Excel files and Word documents and will be stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?
On the INALE server and clouds hosted by the coordinator.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
We will use data from previous projects to model Mediterranean seaweed species about temperature.
What is the expected size of the data?
Limited space is required; 1 GB should be sufficient.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Our data are subject to patents and joint publications, so no other parties can have access to them.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in some cases, to engage the citizens, but data in terms of communication rather than dissemination.

7.6. Task 3.5 Upscaling seaweed cultivation in earthen ponds (Lead: [CTQ])

Partner involved: CTQ

CTQ
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to seaweed growth and seeding evaluations will be created, analyzed, and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Raw data from seaweed growth and seeding evaluations, processed data in Office Excel, Word, PowerPoint documents and statistical software (R), and data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
Depending on the amount of graphic material (photos, short videos), probably max. 1 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Will use data from similar experiments in previous projects for comparison, and trace the effect of optimization and the potential of scale-up...
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties upon request after consultation with CTAQUA and lead partner. Data will be mainly of interest to seaweed farmers and academics.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?

Yes, in that case they will be published on Open Access journals or as Green Open Access, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners following the stipulations of the GA and the CA.

8. WP4 Verification of existing & new developments for processing algae, fish, and extraction of compounds

This WP aims to develop mathematical models, improve energy/cost efficiency in the algae drying process, optimize and validate an existing extraction process, obtain functional protein products from novel cultivated, and improve nutritional value and algae digestibility through the efficient, up-scaled, bacterial-based composition of cell-wall.

8.1. Task 4.1. Modeling and simulation of biorefinery processes for an optimized up-scaling (Lead: [IDE])

Partner involved: IDE

IDE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the development of several optimized mathematical models of the biorefinery processes at the technical and/or economic level will be created and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, word documents, excel files, and Python files will be generated and stored on the cloud storage of Microsoft (e.g. OneDrive, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Experimental data from the biorefinery processes will be used to adjust the required experimental parameters for the model implementation
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 20 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

8.2.Task 4.2. Drying and microwave enhancement (Lead: [IDE])

Partners involved: IDE, UCC

IDE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Determine the most effective methods and procedures for the utilization of MW in the processes of spray drying and macroalgal drying.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Numerical simulation results (.mph files) and real data of microalgae drying experiments.
Where will it be stored?
On IDENER's server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
SoA of microalgae drying methods and procedures by MW will be reviewed.
What is the expected size of the data?
≤1GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners and, if possible, reviewed data will be published in a scientific journal as a Review.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes.

UCC
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Microalga biomass drying and enhancement. Optimization of biomass gelation properties and extracts
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Numeric Excel databases, powerpoints, and Word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the co-ordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 5 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes

8.3. Task 4.3. Microwave commission and finetuning (Lead: [IDE])

Partner involved: IDE

IDE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Adjust the MW drying parameters to real samples and demonstrate the process utility in a relevant environment.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Prototype designs, and experimental results of the drying process.
Where will it be stored?
On IDENER's server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Yes. Existing data of current drying protocols will be compared to the developed ones.
What is the expected size of the data?
≤1GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

8.4. Task 4.4. Verification of an existing process for protein ingredients production from fish (Leader – [BII])

Partner involved: BII

BII
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the biorefining process and associated processing parameters of selected fish biomass will be created and stored. Yields achieved and nutritional parameters of protein ingredients produced during industrial-scale trials will be measured and recorded.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Data will be collected in Excel files, word files, and powerpoint presentations, and emails will be shared with the WP- leader and coordinator via cloud storage of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
BII's server
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 4-5 GB.

Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data files will be shared with the project coordinator WP leads and partners. Data will be provided to official parties upon request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

8.5. Task 4.5 Demonstrating the bacterial-based algal-polysaccharides decomposition for improving algae nutritional value and digestibility (Lead: [IOLR])

Partner involved: IOLR

IOLR Task 4.5 Task 4.6
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the efficiency of the developed bioreactor and operation conditions will be created and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word and Excel documents will be generated and stored by the PI. A patent application will be submitted by the PI.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
< 5GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Part of the data will be accessible only to the PI (for patent application). Other data will be shared by the PI with relevant partners in the project. Some data will be released as scientific manuscript/s for publication.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes

8.6. Task 4.6 Finetuning and upscaling of the bacterial-enzymatic reactor for algae decomposition (Lead: [IOLR])

Partner involved: IOLR - Data Management was already provided combined with Task 4.5

8.7. Task 4.7 Macroalgae-based eco-packaging boxes (Lead: [AWI])

Partner involved: AWI

AWI
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to macro algae-based eco-packaging boxes will be created, stored, presented at international conferences, used for educational purposes, and published in open-access journals (as appropriate).
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, word documents, excel spreadsheets, PowerPoint presentations will be generated and stored on the cloud storage of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or SharePoint, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On SharePoint and the AWI server
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 10 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only until open-access publication. Prior to publication, non-sensitive data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Some generated data related to packaging production may be sensitive/protected and not made publicly available/published.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes

8.8. Task 4.8 Upscaling a methodology for bycatches and algae biomass processing and valorization (Lead: [CTQ])

Partner involved: CTQ

CTQ
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to methodology for bycatch and algae biomass processing and valorization will be created, analyzed, and stored.

What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Raw data from shelf-life analyses trials, questionnaires/interviews with fishermen and fish market, biomass data bycatch material (incl. photos, videos), recipes food processing data, and food market data, processed data in Office Excel, Word, PowerPoint documents and statistical software (R), data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
Depending on the amount of graphic material (photos, short videos), probably max. 1 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Similar types of information collected in the framework of previous projects such as the INTER-REG-POCTEP ATLAZULand private projects will be used as the basis for developing scale-up models and expanding these datasets.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties upon request after consultation with CTAQUA and the lead partner. Data will be mainly of interest to fishermen, the general fish market, and food processing industry/retail.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in that case they will be published on Open Access journals or as Green Open Access, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners following the stipulations of the GA and the CA.

9. WP5 Properties evaluation, formulation, novel functional products, and biosecurity

WP5 aims to develop novel aquafeeds and novel functional foods for human consumption based on cultivated macroalgae from WP1-WP3, microalgae (from WP3), algae extracts (from WP4), invertebrate biomass from beach wracks (from WP4) and processed bycatches (from WP4).

9.1. Task 5.1 Evaluation of algae and extracts properties (Lead: [UGE])

Partners involved: UGE, ANF

UGE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to evaluation of algae and extracts properties will be created, analysed and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Raw data from analytical evaluations, processed data in Office Excel, Word and PowerPoint documents, data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.

What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 15 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in case they will be published on Open Access journals, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners.

ANF
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to functional properties of extracts will be generated and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails and Excel sheets with the laboratory results will be created and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (Outlook, Specific folder of NOVAFOODIES project in One Drive). Word documents with the methodology and main results will be generated and stored on ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 5 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, with the prior consent of the project partners

9.2. Task 5.2 Formulation, development, and validation of innovative aquafeeds (Lead: CTQ)

Partners involved: CTQ, UGE

UGE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to formulation, development, and validation of innovative aquafeeds will be created, analysed and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?

Raw data from analytical evaluations, processed data in Office Excel, Word and PowerPoint documents, data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 15 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in case they will be published on Open Access journals, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners.

CTQ
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to formulation, development, and validation of innovative aquafeeds will be created, analysed and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Raw data from analytical evaluations, processed data in Office Excel, Word and PowerPoint documents, data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 15 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Similar type of information collected in the framework of previous projects such as the INTER-REG-POCTEP ATLAZUL and private projects will be used as basis for developing scale-up models and expand these datasets.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in case they will be published on Open Access journals, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners.

9.4. Task 5.3 Formulation, development, and validation of functional food for human consumption (Lead: TUCN)

Partners involved: TUCN – Subtask 5.3.3., CTQ Subtask 5.3.1., UCC Subtask 5.3.2., JOTIS Subtask 5.3.4.

TUCN Task 5.3 Subtask 5.3.3
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the development of new functional foods for human consumption based on macroalgae extracts will be created, partially published, and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Results of the physical-chemical-nutritional analysis of developed food products will be generated. The data will be collected and stored as Word, Excel, PowerPoint, and ShareFile documents.
Where will it be stored?
The data will be on the cloud storage of Microsoft hosted by the coordinator, on the TUCN (P9) server, and on researchers' databases.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
No data will be re-used, and all results will be original.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to all project partners. With the permission of the coordinator and partners, some experimental results could be disseminated at scientific events (conferences, symposiums) or by publishing in an ISI-ranked journal.
Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes. Some experimental data could be presented at scientific events or published in journals, but only after the permission of the coordinator and partners is obtained.

CTQ
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the development of novel foods from fisheries bycatch and seaweed biomass will be created, analyzed, and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Raw data from extract bioactivity analyses, aquafeed diet formulations, fish nutritional trials (incl. performance, immunology, digestibility trials, etc.) incl. photos and videos processed data in Office Excel, Word, PowerPoint documents and statistical software (R), data communicated by email will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.

Where will it be stored?
On our server.
What is the expected size of the data?
Depending on the amount of graphic material (photos, short videos), probably max. 1 GB.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible to interested official parties upon request after consultation with CTAQUA and the lead partner. Data will be mainly of interest to aquafeed producers and fish farmers.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, in that case, they will be published on Open Access journals or as Green Open Access, after consultation and agreement with the other project partners following the stipulations of the GA and the CA.

UCC
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Optimization extracts organoleptic properties and stability.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Numeric Excel databases, powerpoints, and Word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 5 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes

JOTIS Task 5.3 Subtask 5.3.4
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the functional products that will be developed within the frame of the project will be created and stored..

What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Word documents, excel files and photographs will be generated and the information contained in these files will be included in the project's deliverables.
Where will it be stored?
The files will be stored on the JOTIS server
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The company will use existing know-how for the product development. Any data that will be generated for the project will be new.
What is the expected size of the data?
Approximately 2GB
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
The data will be shared only with the consortium partners. The data will be accessible royalty-free strictly on a need-to-know basis and in the context of the work plan as defined in the Grant Agreement. For exploitation of Results, Access Rights have to be requested to be granted by JOTIS on Fair and Reasonable Conditions. To other partners of the consortium
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

9.5. Task 5.4 Biosecurity assessments for new products (Lead: [ANF])

Partner involved: ANF

ANF
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the biosecurity of new products will be generated and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails and Excel sheets with the laboratory results will be created and stored on the cloud storage of Microsoft (Outlook, Specific folder of NOVAFOODIES project in One Drive). Word documents with the methodology and main results, also from other partners, will be generated and stored on ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 5 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes, with the prior consent of the project partners

10. WP6 IT tools development and monitoring for traceability and enhanced trust

This WP aims to define and optimize value chains that enable the development of circular business models in the fisheries, aquaculture, and seaweed sectors. To develop tools and devices for a transparent traceability and trusted environment among the value-chain stakeholders. To develop an online MarketPlace for fish and aquaculture products, to offer at least 100 producers and wholesale customers a high technology innovation platform traceability in value-chain, including quality/ biosecurity assessment data for new products. To develop a user-friendly app for consumers and end-users to gain trust in the value chain by food traceability including quality/biosecurity assessments, reaching ≥ 1000 users.

10.1. Task 6.1. Optimized models for circularity in aquaculture (Lead: [ITE])

Partner involved: ITE

ITE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The purpose of data collection in this project is to gather comprehensive and real-time information related to various aspects of the fisheries, aquaculture, and seaweed sectors. This data is crucial for achieving the project's main objectives, which involve developing optimized circular value chains, creating transparent traceability tools, establishing an online marketplace, and designing a user-friendly app.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Reports (word documents), E-mails Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ITENE SharePoint, hosted by ITENE.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data analyzed will be provided by partners, each information depends on the partner involved.
What is the expected size of the data?
Excel files and online surveys, so the reserved space for this data is 3 GB.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

10.2. Task 6.2. Monitoring systems for complete traceability (Lead: [ITE])

Partner involved: ITE

ITE
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
An IoT-based system and device will be developed to provide in real-time, and with the required frequency, information to assess the quality and degradation levels of raw materials handling and uses.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Reports (word documents), 2D drawings (CAD models), electronic layouts, E-mails Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ITENE SharePoint, hosted by ITENE.
Where will it be stored?
On our own server and InfoTeam (IT) server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data analyzed is novel, each information comes from measuring devices installed.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 3 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

10.3. Task 6.3. NOVAFOODIES MarketPlace digital platform (Lead: [IT])

Partner involved: IT

IT
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The collected data contribute to the intended purpose of the WP to provide a B2B platform for supply chain monitoring and traceability.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
The system will collect data related to batches of food products, provided by IoT systems, such as the type of product, its origin, the date of capture or processing, etc.
Where will it be stored?
The data will be processed and stored on the dedicated cloud computing platform for the project.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The acquired data will potentially be used in an aggregated form for data analysis purposes and for the technological enhancement of the platform.
What is the expected size of the data?
It depends on the number of transactions acquired during the MarketPlace Experimental Phase; however, it could potentially be in the order of tens of gigabytes.

To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
The collected data will be shared with project partners or for dissemination of results, if required, in accordance with the Data Management Plan. The collected data could be useful to both private and public-sector organizations in the industry for implementing food supply chain safety policies.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
The collected and generated data could be of interest, and we will make them available to the consortium.

10.4. Task 6.4. NOVAFOODIES App for end-users (Lead: [IT])

Partner involved: IT

IT
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The collected data contribute to the intended purpose of the WP to provide end-consumers with access to supply chain monitoring and traceability.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
The system will display collected data related to batches of food products provided by IoT systems, such as product type, origin, capture or processing date, etc. The mobile application will not collect personal user data, as it does not require user registration.
Where will it be stored?
Some system data may be stored in the user's local device memory.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
In the order of a few kilobytes.
What is the expected size of the data?
No, they will not be collected and, therefore, will not be reused.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
There is no such collection/sharing. No data utility
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No data to share

12. WP7 Value chain sustainability, socio-laboral inclusion and standardisation

This WP quantifies and evaluates the effects on the environment of the proposed solutions, compared to existing solutions or industry practices, assesses the economic impact of the innovations (incl. costs, benefits drivers & structure), and evaluates its feasibility to create new or enter existing markets, identify cost reduction opportunities, and mitigate risks.

12.1. Task 7.1 Environmental impacts evaluation (LCA) (Lead: [HOL])

Partner involved: HOL

HOL
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The data collected from the partners and the process will be used to elaborate the LCA in order to assess the environmental impacts of the process.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, Excel, and Word documents, as well as reports, should be produced and saved inside the cloud storage systems provided by Microsoft, such as Outlook, Teams/SharePoint, or ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The allotted storage capacity for this material is 6GB if necessary.
What is the expected size of the data?
All of the data collected for this study will be entirely novel.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
Data will be accessible to the project partners.
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
According to the Grant Agreement, Data and Deliverables were classified as Sensitive.

12.2. Task 7.2 Economic impacts evaluation (LCC) (Lead: [HOL])

Partner involved: HOL

HOL
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The data collected from the partners and the process will be used to elaborate the LCC in order to assess the economic impacts of all the processes.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, Excel, and Word documents, as well as reports, should be produced and saved inside the cloud storage systems provided by Microsoft, such as Outlook, Teams/SharePoint, or ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?

On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The allotted storage capacity for this material is 6GB if necessary.
What is the expected size of the data?
All of the data collected for this study will be entirely novel.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
Data will be accessible to the project partners.
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
According to the Grant Agreement, Data and Deliverables were classified as Sensitive.

12.3. Task 7.3 Social and Gender Assessments (Lead: [ACH])

Partners involved: ACH, HOL

ACH
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data collection about social impacts on human capital, human well-being, gender balance, cultural heritage, social economy, and social behaviour of the project solutions. Data collection to assess the social inclusion and gender issues during each phase of the production development (finetuning of processes, scale-up designs, and elaboration of final products) in order to provide recommendations to each developing and industrial partner to control or eliminate differential impacts for disadvantaged groups, with a dedicated part related to gender.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Data will be collected from emails between partners and associated partners, surveys in google forms of Microsoft forms and the corresponding answers. Data generated will be word documents and will be stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator and by the partner in charge of the activity and corresponding deliverables.
Where will it be stored?
On ACH and LDA servers and in the coordinators's server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Data resources coming from partners will be used. Data will be collected about other studies related to gender approaches and good practices in the sector, and they will be referenced in the documents generated.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager. The collection of any personal and sensitive data is not foreseen.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes.

HOL
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
The data collected from the partners and the process will be used to elaborate the s-LCA in order to assess the s-LCA of all the processes.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, Excel and Word documents, as well as reports, should be produced and saved inside the cloud storage systems provided by Microsoft, such as Outlook, Teams/SharePoint, or ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
The allotted storage capacity for this material is 6GB if necessary.
What is the expected size of the data?
All of the data collected for this study will be entirely novel.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions?
Data will be accessible to the project partners.
To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Project partners.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
According to the Grant Agreement, Data and Deliverables were classified as Sensitive.

12.4. Task 7.4 Training activities (Lead: [LVA])

Partners involved: LVA – Subtask 7.4.3 and 7.4.4, ACH – Subtask 7.3 and 7.4

LVA Task 7.4 Subtask 7.4.3 Subtask 7.4.4
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Vocational Education and Training (VET) content will be created by ACH and LVA, both for online and in use. Additionally, a Training Handbook will be written, translated into several languages, and distributed amongst partners. The purpose of the training is to relay information gathered in the NOVAFOODIES project to students.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Digital documents (emails, written documents, presentations, transcripts, etc.) and printed physical documents (training descriptions, handouts, etc.). All digital documents will be stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator and on the company's own servers.
Where will it be stored?
On our own servers. In the cloud storage.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All novel data will come from previous tasks/work packages of the NOVAFOODIES project. Reused assets will stem from previous training material created by LVA and ACH, as well as from publications dealing with recent developments in innovative teaching and training strategies.

What is the expected size of the data?
N/A
With whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
The data will be accessible to the project partners through the shared cloud. Created materials will be additionally made available to participants of the training activities, workshops, seminars, and e-learning courses. Access will be granted by task-relevant partners.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

ACH Task 7.3 Task 7.4
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data collection about social impacts on human capital, human well-being, gender balance, cultural heritage, social economy, and social behaviour of the project solutions. Data collection to assess the social inclusion and gender issues during each phase of the production development (finetuning of processes, scale-up designs, and elaboration of final products) in order to provide recommendations to each developing and industrial partner to control or eliminate differential impacts for disadvantaged groups, with a dedicated part related to gender.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Data will be collected from emails between partners and associated partners, surveys in google forms of Microsoft forms and the corresponding answers. Data generated will be word documents and will be stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator and by the partner in charge of the activity and corresponding deliverables.
Where will it be stored?
On ACH and LDA servers and in the coordinators' server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
Data resources coming from partners will be used. Data will be collected about other studies related to gender approaches and good practices in the sector, and they will be referenced in the documents generated.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
To whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request. Access will be granted by the project manager. The collection of any personal and sensitive data is not foreseen.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
Yes.

12.5. Task 7.5 Standardisation roadmap (Lead: [ASRO])

Partner involved: ASRO

ASRO	
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?	Data related to formal standardization will be collected and analyzed
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?	Xcell documents and Word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storage of Microsoft or share-file hosted by the coordinator
Where will it be stored?	On ASRO`s desktop and personal computers in the first phase
Will you re-use any existing data and how?	We will see for the analysis existing national/European/international standards. The conclusions and recommendations will be new.
What is the expected size of the data?	Lists with a few hundred standards with initiatives, names, scopes, development organization, etc., 25-30 texts of standards that will be analyzed during the project implementation, and finally a Standardization Roadmap, about 50-80 pages
With whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?	Data will be accessible to the project partners, the result of the analysis will be shared with selected stakeholders from outside the project, and the conclusions and recommendations from the Standardization Roadmap will be public. To the European standardization network, to policymakers in the area of the project, other researchers in the area of the project
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?	The result of the desk research regarding existing standards and standardization document will be public (the Standardization Roadmap)

13. WP8 Dissemination, exploitation, clustering, and engagement

WP8 raises awareness of the project's results amongst key target audiences, develops plans to support exploitation and ensure the sustainability of project know-how and results in the value chain, promotes networking with other projects, and engages stakeholders/consumers outside the consortium, increasing trust and fostering future collaborations and business opportunities.

13.2. Task 8.1 Plan for exploitation and dissemination of results (PEDR) (Lead: [LCI])

Partner involved: LCI, SPES – SPES data for this task is explained in the description of data related to Task 8.2 and 8.5

LCI Task 8.1 Task 8.4
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the exploitation of the project results will be created and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails and Word documents, Excel sheets will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

13.3. Task 8.2 Communication and dissemination activities (Lead: [SPES])

Partner involved: SPES

SPES Task 8.1 Task 8.2
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
SPES will use data related to communication and dissemination materials to promote the NOVA-FOODIES project and each partner that is part of the Consortium. SPES will do so to maximize the dissemination of the Project activities and to involve stakeholders.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails, word documents, flyers, brochures, websites, and posts for social media. The material will be available online and in the Project ShareFile.
Where will it be stored?
In our own server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?

All data will be new.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space should be less than 15 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to partners of the project and interested stakeholders (e.g. website with partners presentations will be public, project brochure could be downloaded by interested users). The data might be useful for any stakeholders interested in NOVAFOODIES activities.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

13.4. Task 8.3 Clustering activities (Lead: [SPES])

Partner involved: SPES

SPES
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data collected under this Task are useful to identify possible collaborations with other EU projects sharing the same topic, thus expanding the dissemination of NOVAFOODIES activities and involving stakeholders with interest in the main focus.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
E.g. Excel tables with data about Projects, and a list of participants in events organized under this Task (name, surname, emails of stakeholders). The material will be available in the Project Share-File.
Where will it be stored?
In our own server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be new.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space should be about 10 MB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data of stakeholders involved will be accessible to partners of the project only. Possible collaboration with other projects will be disseminated, with no sharing of sensitive data.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

13.5. Task 8.4 IP management, Exploitation of results and business models (Lead: [LCI])

Partner involved: LCI - Data Management was already provided combined with Task 8.4

13.6. Task 8.5 Stakeholder engagement and co-creation (Lead: [SPES])

Partner involved: SPES

SPES Task 8.1 Task 8.5
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data collected under this Task will draw a communication and consultation process with stakeholders.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Email, Word and Excel documents, and G-forms to collect needed info. The material will be available in the Project ShareFile. Data will be public to the extent established by the Task itself-
Where will it be stored?
In our own server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be new.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space will be about 10 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be shared with NOVAFOODIES partners. Any results driven from surveys will be published anonymously.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

14. WP9 Project management

Guarantees that the project is carried out correctly by the objectives set, avoiding and resolving possible risks and problems that may arise, and being in continuous contact with the consortium and the EC.

14.1. Task 9.1 Overall coordination (Lead: [IDE])

14.2. Task 9.2 Financial and administrative management (Lead: [IDE])

Partner involved: IDE

There is no DMP collected from IDE of these tasks because there are no data expected to be generated in this WP.

14.3. Task 9.3 Data Management (Lead: [LCI])

LCI
What is the purpose of the data collection/generation and its relation to the objectives of the project?
Data related to the data management plan of the project will be created and stored.
What types and formats of data will the project/task generate/collect?
Emails and Word documents will be generated and stored on the cloud storages of Microsoft (e.g. Outlook, Teams/SharePoint), or ShareFile, hosted by the coordinator.
Where will it be stored?
On our server.
Will you re-use any existing data and how?
All data will be novel.
What is the expected size of the data?
The reserved space for this data is 6 GB.
Whom will the data be shared? Under what conditions? To whom might the data be useful ('data utility')?
Data will be accessible to the project partners only. Data will be accessible, to interested official parties on request.
Will you generate any research data that could be shared publicly (part of open science)?
No.

15. Data storage timeline

Partners are expected to keep any data generated on this project for the duration of the project and seven years after. Data intended for general public use will be uploaded to Zenodo where it will be held indefinite time and be available free of charge. The Webpage will be live for two years after the project ends.